

Fluorescence Studies of Chicken Serum Albumin Interactions with Drugs

C. I. ANUNUSO

School of Earth, Mineral and Natural Sciences, Federal University of Technology, P. M. B. 1526, Owerri, Nigeria

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The binding of either dicoumarol or warfarin to chicken serum albumin (CSA) quenches the native tyrosine fluorescence of the protein. The interaction results in an increase in the intrinsic fluorescence of warfarin and a shift in the wavelength of maximal emission from 400 to 395 nm. An increase in the intrinsic fluorescence of dansylglycine on binding to CSA is accompanied by a blue-shift in the wavelength of maximal emission of the drug, thus indicating the hydrophobic nature of the binding sites for these drugs.

CSA has one strong affinity site for warfarin ($K=3.7 \times 10^6 M^{-1}$) as well as an intermediate number of much weaker sites. The protein has three strong affinity sites for dicoumarol with an average K of $6.8 \times 10^6 M^{-1}$ and several number of much weaker (secondary) sites.

THE interaction between a drug and a protein probably influences its biological activity and such an interaction may play an important role in governing the drug's absorption, distribution and excretory characteristics. Albumin is the principal plasma protein and plays an important role in plasma-protein binding of most drugs as well as interacting with many endogeneous materials e.g. fatty acids. The function of albumin is probably to transport compounds to the cell membrane and to act as a 'store' for these compounds since these compounds are considered inactive when bound to albumin.

Experimental

A Baird-Atomic Fluoripoint spectrofluorimeter with manual and automatic scanning on both monochromators was used. Fluorescence spectra were scanned at a speed of 1 mm s^{-1} . A Unicam Sp600 spectrophotometer was used for optical density measurements for protein concentration.

Fluorescence titrations were carried out with $1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$ CSA (2 ml) while adding aliquots of the drug ($1 \times 10^{-5} M$ in sodium phosphate buffer pH 7.4, molarity 1×10^{-2}) from a microsyringe. After mixing the solutions, the change in fluorescence intensity was measured.

Crystalline CSA (98% pure, mol. wt. 65000), warfarin, 3-(α -acetylbenzyl)-4-hydroxycoumarin, dicoumarol, 3,3-methylenebis(4-hydroxycoumarin) and dansylglycine (*N,N*-dimethylamino-1-naphthalene-5-sulphonyl-*N*-glycine) (Sigma) were used and all other chemicals were of reagent grade.

Results and Discussion

The native tyrosine fluorescence of CSA monitored at 300 nm while exciting at 280 nm, was quenched as aliquots of warfarin was added to a solution of the protein. Binding of dicoumarol to CSA also quenched the fluorescence of tyrosine at 300 nm with excitation at 280 nm. A similar quenching of the protein (tyrosine) was observed at the same wavelengths when bound to dansylglycine. The decrease in the fluorescence of the protein was rapid when the moles of drug/protein ratio is below unity. This represents a 1 : 1 stoichiometric binding interactions.

Intrinsic warfarin fluorescence was enhanced when bound to CSA (Fig. 1). The Scatchard plot (not shown) of the data for the fluorescence enhancement of warfarin (Fig. 1) suggests that CSA has one strong binding site for warfarin with an association constant of $3.7 \times 10^6 M^{-1}$. The protein, CSA has other intermediate binding sites for the drug with an association constant of $0.45 \times 10^6 M^{-1}$. The binding of warfarin to CSA was accompanied by a blue-shift of 5 nm in the wavelength of maximal emission (Fig. 2). Binding of dansylglycine to CSA was also accompanied by a blue-shift of 62 nm (Fig. 3). The binding of dansylglycine to CSA was displaced by dicoumarol (Fig. 4). Scatchard plot (not shown) of the binding of dicoumarol to CSA suggests that CSA has three strong sites for dicoumarol with an association constant of $8.0 \times 10^6 M^{-1}$.

The increase in the fluorescence of warfarin at 400 nm with excitation at 320 nm was due to the displacement of the drug warfarin from CSA binding site by dicoumarol. Extrapolation of the linear

Fig. 1. Warfarin fluorescence enhancement on binding to CSA. Intensity of fluorescence was monitored at 400 nm while exciting at 320 nm, bandwidth of excitation and emission = 8 nm.

Fig. 2. Fluorescence emission spectra of warfarin and CSA, obtained by excitation at 380 nm bandwidth of excitation and emission were = 8 nm; concentrations: CSA = $1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$; warfarin, $1 \times 10^{-5} M$; warfarin alone (2 ml) = $1 \times 10^{-5} M$; warfarin - CSA complex (2 ml) warfarin ($1 \times 10^{-5} M$) + CSA (1 ml) = $1 \times 5 \times 10^{-5} M$.

Fig. 3. Uncorrected fluorescence emission spectra of 1:1 mixture of CSA ($1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$) + dansylglycine ($1 \times 10^{-4} M$) and dansylglycine alone ($1 \times 10^{-4} M$), bandwidth of excitation and emission = 8 nm.

Fig. 4. Dansylglycine fluorescence: displacement of dansylglycine from CSA binding by dicoumarol (f_s = fluorescence of displaced dansylglycine); the intensity of fluorescence was monitored at 480 nm while excitation at 350 nm; bandwidths of excitation and emission = 8 nm; silica cuvette contains (2 ml) CSA ($1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$) and dansylglycine ($1 \times 10^{-4} M$) and titrated with dicoumarol ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$).

portions of the fluorescence titration curve (not shown) shows a 1:3 CSA - dicoumarol binding. The Scatchard plot (not shown) of the binding data has shown that CSA has three strong binding sites for dicoumarol with an association constant of $5.5 \times 10^6 M^{-1}$. Binding of the drug to other intermediate CSA sites did occur with an association constant of $2.2 \times 10^6 M^{-1}$.

The binding of warfarin to CSA is accompanied by resonance energy transfer from the protein to the bound drug through a single site. Resonance energy transfer from the protein tyrosine groups to bound drug is feasible on energetic considerations through the overlap of the absorption band of warfarin and the emission band of CSA^{3,5}. Resonance energy transfer may be enhanced by protein conformational changes. Conformational changes may have taken place due to the heterogeneous nature of the CSA binding sites.

The blue-shift in the maximal emission (Fig. 2) when warfarin binds to CSA suggests that the drug was bound to the hydrophobic or apolar region of the protein. It thus appears that a hydrophobic environment can enhance fluorescence and that the drug must be properly oriented with respect to the protein so that interaction with the hydrophobic region of the protein could take place. Furthermore, it seems that hydrophobic bonds are significant forces which hold the drug-protein complex together. However, this does not imply that other non-covalent bonds and ionic bonds are less significant.

Studies on CSA - warfarin binding has shown that CSA has one strong binding site for warfarin with an association constant of $3.7 \times 10^6 M^{-1}$. The non-linearity of the Scatchard plot is due to the presence of other intermediate (secondary sites) binding sites for the drug. The association constant for these secondary sites are ten times lower than that of the primary site. The presence of two classes of binding sites is further supported by the two

stages of CSA-warfarin binding: rapid primary binding followed by slow protein conformation. Protein conformation is probably due to minor changes in the environment brought about by the presence of warfarin or any other drug that is capable of altering the physical properties of the protein. Protein conformation is apparent at high drug to protein ratios.

The binding of dansylglycine to a single CSA site was accompanied by an increase in the intrinsic fluorescence of the dye and a blue-shift of 62 nm, hence the dye was used as a probe for the polarity of CSA-dicoumarol binding site.

Competitive displacement studies were carried out to demonstrate the versatile binding characteristic of CSA. Dicoumarol by competitively displacing dansylglycine from CSA binding has shown that dicoumarol binds to a hydrophobic region of the protein (Fig. 4). The protein has three strong affinity sites for dicoumarol with an association constant of $8.0 \times 10^6 M^{-1}$. The presence of three strong binding sites in CSA for dicoumarol was supported by the competitive displacement of warfarin from CSA by dicoumarol with an association constant of $5.5 \times 10^6 M^{-1}$. An average K value of $6.8 \times 10^6 M^{-1}$ is probably more likely.

Differences in the magnitude of K , the association constant values for the two classes of sites, are probably due to differences in the structural parameter of the protein presented to the binding ligand or due to interactions between sites which tend to accentuate or attenuate binding affinities. Absolute

binding affinity may be obtained with a single type of binding site.

The ability of dicoumarol to competitively displace warfarin and dansylglycine from CSA binding may be interpreted as demonstrating that the binding sites of these drugs are sufficiently close together to that dicoumarol can interact with both sites simultaneously. It has been shown earlier that the binding sites of these drugs are located in the hydrophobic or apolar region of CSA. Displacement of warfarin and dansylglycine from CSA binding by dicoumarol is probably due to conformational changes in the presence of dicoumarol. This suggests that the high forces of association for the drug-CSA complex are at the same time weak enough so that minor modifications of the physical environment produced by the presence of dicoumarol are sufficient to cause dissociation of the CSA-drug complex.

CSA contains probably three separate primary sites. Conformational changes in the albumin molecule result in the uncovering of one or more of these sites.

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